

The Role of Cybersecurity Awareness in Safeguarding Digital Systems in Institution of Higher Learning

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Abstract

This study investigates the role of cybersecurity awareness in safeguarding digital systems within institutions of higher learning in the North Central region of Nigeria. As educational institutions increasingly adopt digital technologies, cybersecurity has become a critical concern. A descriptive survey design was employed to address three research questions focusing on awareness levels, prevalent threats, and strategies for improvement. The study sampled 168 participants including students, lecturers, and administrators from the Federal University of Education, Kontagora, and Abdullahi Kure University, Minna. Data were collected using a structured, expert-validated questionnaire with strong internal consistency (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.82), and analyzed through descriptive statistics. Findings revealed disparities in cybersecurity awareness across groups, with phishing, malware, and data breaches being the most common threats. The study recommends implementing compulsory cybersecurity training, enhancing ICT infrastructure, establishing a national policy tailored to tertiary institutions, and conducting continuous awareness campaigns. Further research is suggested to explore behavioral factors influencing cybersecurity practices in Nigerian higher education.

Introduction

The rapid advancement of digital technology has significantly impacted various sectors, including education. In Nigeria, University of Education play a crucial role in training future educators who are expected to integrate technology into their teaching and learning processes. As digital tools become more embedded in education, the importance of cybersecurity awareness has increased. Cybersecurity awareness refers to the knowledge and practices individuals adopt to protect personal and institutional data from cyber threats such as phishing, identity theft, hacking, and malware attacks. Despite the growing dependence on technology, many students and lecturers in Nigerian Universities of Education lack adequate awareness of cybersecurity risks, leaving them vulnerable to cyber threats (Ogundele et al., 2023).

Educational institutions worldwide have increasingly become targets for cybercriminals due to the vast amounts of sensitive data they handle, including students' personal information, academic records, and financial data. Nigerian Universities of Education are not exempted from these threats. Reports indicate a rise in cyber fraud, data breaches, and digital identity theft within educational institutions in Nigeria (Aliyu et al., 2021; Garba & Othman, 2021). Many students and staff inadvertently expose themselves to cyber risks through unsafe internet practices, weak passwords, and a lack of knowledge on recognizing malicious online activities. The absence of structured cybersecurity training programs further exacerbates this issue, increasing institutional vulnerability to attacks (Bozkus Kahyaoglu & Caliyurt, 2018; Information Security Forum (ISF), 2016; Vincent, 2024).

According to Ogundele et al., (2023) a major cybersecurity challenge in Nigeria today is the prevalence of cyber fraud, commonly referred to as "Yahoo-Yahoo," which involves online scams, phishing, and financial fraud, often perpetrated by youths. The lack of cybersecurity awareness among students in Universities of Education may contribute to the spread of this problem in two ways: some students become perpetrators due to peer influence, financial desperation, or lack of ethical digital knowledge, while others fall victim to these schemes due to their ignorance of cybersecurity best practices (Aliyu et al., 2021). The weak enforcement of cybersecurity policies within educational institutions further exposes students and staff to the dangers of cyber fraud (Njoku et al., 2019; Osijirin et al., 2025).

One of the key reasons for the low cybersecurity awareness in Nigerian Universities of Education is the absence of a dedicated cybersecurity curriculum. While computer science and ICT-related courses cover general digital literacy, cybersecurity concepts are often overlooked or insufficiently addressed. This knowledge gap means that students, even those in technology-related fields, graduate without proper cybersecurity skills. Additionally, many lecturers and non-teaching staff lack the necessary training to identify and prevent cyber threats, resulting in a weak cybersecurity culture within these institutions (Awogbami, 2020; Osijirin et al., 2025).

Another significant issue is the inadequate ICT infrastructure in many Nigerian Universities of Education. Many institutions lack secure internet connections, firewalls, and updated antivirus software. In some cases, institutions rely on outdated computer systems that are more vulnerable to security threats. Furthermore, weak institutional cybersecurity policies, poor enforcement of security measures, and resistance from some staff and students to adopt cybersecurity best practices contribute to the low level of awareness. These infrastructure and policy gaps create an environment where cybercriminals, including Yahoo-Yahoo actors, can operate and recruit unsuspecting students into fraudulent activities (Ogundele et al., 2023; Tade & Aliyu, 2011).

The Nigerian government has made efforts to address cybersecurity threats through policies such as the Cybercrime Act 2015, which criminalizes various forms of cyber offenses. However, the implementation of this law within the education sector remains weak, with little emphasis on cybersecurity awareness and compliance in Universities of Education (Ministry & Education, n.d.) . Many institutions do not have specific policies or guidelines mandating cybersecurity training for students and staff, further highlighting the gap between policy formulation and implementation (Garba et al., 2020).

Given these challenges, there is a growing need to assess the level of cybersecurity awareness among students and lecturers in Nigerian Universities of Education. Understanding the extent of awareness, identifying common cyber threats faced by institutions, and evaluating the impact of existing cybersecurity policies and ICT infrastructure will provide valuable insights for improving cybersecurity education in these Universities.

This study, therefore, examines the level of cybersecurity awareness in Nigerian Universities of Education, the challenges faced, and the potential strategies for improving cybersecurity

practices within these institutions. By conducting an empirical investigation, this research will contribute to knowledge on cybersecurity education and offer recommendations for integrating cybersecurity awareness programs into the curriculum of Universities of Education in Nigeria. Such initiatives will not only help in reducing vulnerabilities to cyber threats but also serve as a preventive measure against the proliferation of cyber fraud activities like Yahoo-Yahoo among students

Problem Statement

Despite the integration of digital tools into teaching, learning, and administration in Nigerian Universities of Education, cybersecurity threats remain a significant challenge. Human vulnerability, driven by low cybersecurity awareness and human error, weakens information security and exposes systems to risks such as phishing attacks, malware infections, and identity theft. The large number of system users in academic environments further increases susceptibility to these threats, especially in the absence of robust cybersecurity policies and awareness programs. While Nigeria's Cybercrime Act 2015 provides a legal framework for cybersecurity, its implementation in educational institutions has been limited, leaving gaps in policy enforcement and best practices (Nigeria's Cybercrime Act, 2015).

Although cybersecurity research in Nigerian higher education has largely centered on conventional universities and polytechnics, universities of education have received minimal scholarly attention despite their growing reliance on digital systems for teaching, learning, and administration. The extent to which these institutions enforce cybersecurity policies and educate students and staff on digital security remains unclear. Additionally, challenges such as inadequate ICT infrastructure, weak institutional policies, and the lack of structured cybersecurity training further hinder awareness. Without addressing these gaps, Universities of Education remain vulnerable to cyber threats, posing risks to institutional data security and the digital safety of students and lecturers. The study assessed cybersecurity awareness in North-Central Universities of Education, identify key challenges, and propose strategies for strengthening cybersecurity education and practices

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to assess cybersecurity awareness in Nigerian Universities of Education and explore ways to improve it. Specifically, the study aims to:

1. Assess the level of cybersecurity awareness among students and lecturers in the Universities of Education.
2. Identify the key cybersecurity threats and challenges faced in the Universities of Education.
3. Propose effective strategies for enhancing cybersecurity education and best practices in Universities of Education.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of cybersecurity awareness among students, lecturers and administrators in Universities of Education?
2. What are the major cybersecurity threats and challenges faced by these educational institutions?
3. What strategies can be implemented to enhance cybersecurity education and best practices in Universities of Education?

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive survey design to examine cybersecurity awareness, threats, and challenges in Nigerian Universities of Education. The study sampled 168 participants including students, lecturers, and administrators from the Federal University of Education, Kontagora, and Abdullahi Kure University, Minna. The primary data collection instrument was a structured questionnaire, divided into three key sections: (1) the extent of cybersecurity awareness among students, lecturers and administrators (2) major cybersecurity threats and challenges in Universities of Education, (3) strategies for enhancing cybersecurity education.

The questionnaire used a four-point Likert scale, ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree. To ensure its validity, the questionnaire was reviewed by three experts in the field of Computer Science, and its reliability was tested using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding a coefficient of 0.82, indicating strong internal consistency. A total of 200 questionnaires were distributed

40 to students, 35 to lecturers and 25 to administrators in each institution. Out of these, 168 completed questionnaires were retrieved, consisting of 72 students, 60 lecturers and 48 administrators, resulting in a response rate of 83.99%. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, specifically mean and standard deviation, to measure participants' agreement levels and response variability.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of cybersecurity awareness among students, lecturers and administrators in Universities of Education?

Table 1: Level of cybersecurity awareness in Universities of Education

S/N	Item Statement		Student	Academic Staff	Administrative Staff
1	I am aware of the importance of cybersecurity in protecting my personal and academic data	N	72	60	48
		Mean	2.59	2.82	2.81
		SD	0.70	0.69	0.48
2	I know how to create and use strong passwords for my online account	N	72	60	48
		Mean	2.61	2.90	2.88
		SD	0.75	0.92	0.44
3	I know how to create and use strong passwords for my online account	N	72	60	48
		Mean	2.35	2.90	2.83
		SD	0.58	0.62	0.62
4	I know how to enable two-factor authentication (2FA) for securing my online accounts	N	72	60	48
		Mean	2.26	2.38	2.92
		SD	0.83	0.89	0.84
5	I frequently receive cybersecurity awareness training or information from my institution	N	72	60	48
		Mean	2.26	2.38	2.92
		SD	0.83	0.89	0.84

As indicated in Table 1, academic staff exhibited the highest awareness regarding the importance of cybersecurity in protecting personal and academic data ($M = 2.82$, $SD = 0.69$), followed by administrative staff ($M = 2.81$, $SD = 0.48$) and students ($M = 2.59$, $SD = 0.70$). In

terms of creating and using strong passwords, awareness was relatively high among academic ($M = 2.90$, $SD = 0.92$) and administrative staff ($M = 2.88$, $SD = 0.44$), with students trailing behind ($M = 2.61$, $SD = 0.75$). Students also showed the least understanding of password management strategies, as reflected by their lower score on the related second item ($M = 2.35$, $SD = 0.58$), compared to academic ($M = 2.90$, $SD = 0.62$) and administrative staff ($M = 2.83$, $SD = 0.62$). Awareness of how to enable two-factor authentication (2FA) was weakest among students ($M = 2.26$, $SD = 0.83$), with academic staff ($M = 2.38$, $SD = 0.89$) slightly ahead and administrative staff demonstrating the highest awareness ($M = 2.92$, $SD = 0.84$). Finally, institutional support in terms of cybersecurity training was rated low across all groups but slightly higher among administrative staff ($M = 2.92$, $SD = 0.84$), while students and academic staff shared lower perceptions ($M = 2.26$, $SD = 0.83$; $M = 2.38$, $SD = 0.89$, respectively). These results suggest that while academic and administrative staff possess relatively higher cybersecurity awareness, students show weaker understanding, especially in practical skills like 2FA and institutional training access, underscoring the need for structured awareness initiatives across all categories

Research Question 2: What are the major cybersecurity threats and challenges faced by these institutions?

Table 2: Major cybersecurity threats and challenges faced by these institutions

S/N	Item Statement		Student	Academic Staff	Administrative Staff
6	I have experienced or witnessed phishing attempts (fraudulent emails, SMS, or calls asking for sensitive information)	N	72	60	48
		Mean	2.28	2.58	3.13
		SD	0.95	0.94	0.83
7	I have encountered malware or viruses affecting my personal or institutional devices	N	72	60	48
		Mean	3.13	3.10	2.92
		SD	0.64	0.54	0.39
8	I have been a victim of identity theft or unauthorized access to my online accounts	N	72	60	48
		Mean	2.53	2.62	2.60
		SD	0.74	0.71	0.75

9	I have experienced financial fraud due to online scams or unauthorized transactions	N	72	60	48
		Mean	2.46	2.73	2.79
		SD	1.04	0.67	0.67
10	I have received fake news, misinformation, or social engineering attacks on social media	N	72	60	48
		Mean	3.19	3.23	2.89
		SD	0.73	0.64	0.36

The results in table2 revealed that that Colleges of Education face diverse cybersecurity threats, with administrative staff reporting the highest exposure to phishing attempts ($M = 3.13$, $SD = 0.83$), suggesting their frequent handling of sensitive data makes them prime targets. Malware and virus attacks were prevalent among students ($M = 3.13$, $SD = 0.64$) and academic staff ($M = 3.10$, $SD = 0.54$), indicating widespread device vulnerability. Incidents of identity theft were reported at similar levels across students ($M = 2.53$, $SD = 0.74$), academic staff ($M = 2.62$, $SD = 0.71$), and administrative staff ($M = 2.60$, $SD = 0.75$). Financial fraud was more pronounced among administrative ($M = 2.79$, $SD = 0.67$) and academic staff ($M = 2.73$, $SD = 0.67$) than students ($M = 2.46$, $SD = 1.04$), reflecting increased exposure in professional roles. The most widespread threat was misinformation and social engineering via social media, with academic staff ($M = 3.23$, $SD = 0.64$) and students ($M = 3.19$, $SD = 0.73$) more affected than administrative staff ($M = 2.89$, $SD = 0.36$). These results emphasize the urgent need for targeted awareness campaigns, strong institutional policies, and proactive cybersecurity training.

Research Question 3: What strategies can be implemented to enhance cybersecurity education and best practices in Universities of Education?

Table 3: Strategies for enhancing cybersecurity education

S/N	Item Statement		Student	Academic Staff	Administrative Staff
11	Cybersecurity awareness training should be made mandatory for all students and lecturers	N	72	60	48
		Mean	2.75	2.96	3.02
		SD	0.64	0.25	0.47

12	The institution should implement stronger policies to enforce cybersecurity practices	N	72	60	48
		Mean	2.48	2.76	2.81
		SD	0.70	0.55	0.39
13	Cybersecurity should be included in the curriculum as a core subject	N	72	60	48
		Mean	2.33	2.86	2.85
		SD	0.62	0.49	0.57
14	Universities should conduct regular security audits and updates on ICT systems	N	72	60	48
		Mean	2.56	2.90	2.95
		SD	0.66	0.47	0.57
15	Awareness campaigns (e.g., posters, emails, and seminars) should be used to educate students and lecturers	N	72	60	48
		Mean	3.03	3.03	2.87
		SD	0.47	0.40	0.59

The findings in table3 showed a general consensus across respondents on the need for structured cybersecurity strategies in Colleges of Education. There was strong agreement that cybersecurity awareness training should be mandatory, with administrative staff expressing the highest support ($M = 3.02$, $SD = 0.47$), followed by academic staff ($M = 2.96$, $SD = 0.25$) and students ($M = 2.75$, $SD = 0.64$). The recommendation for stronger institutional policies also received broad backing, especially among administrative staff ($M = 2.81$, $SD = 0.39$) and academic staff ($M = 2.76$, $SD = 0.55$), while students showed moderate agreement ($M = 2.48$, $SD = 0.70$). Including cybersecurity as a core subject in the curriculum was most supported by academic staff ($M = 2.86$, $SD = 0.49$) and administrative staff ($M = 2.85$, $SD = 0.57$), whereas students were less supportive ($M = 2.33$, $SD = 0.62$), indicating a potential gap in student perception of curriculum relevance. Regular security audits and updates were also deemed necessary, with administrative staff again showing the highest support ($M = 2.95$, $SD = 0.57$), followed closely by academic staff ($M = 2.90$, $SD = 0.47$) and students ($M = 2.56$, $SD = 0.66$). Lastly, awareness campaigns were highly endorsed across all groups, particularly by students ($M = 3.03$, $SD = 0.47$) and academic staff ($M = 3.03$, $SD = 0.40$), reflecting a shared belief in the power of consistent, visible communication. Overall, the results highlight the importance of multi-level interventions including training, policy reforms, curriculum updates, system

audits, and awareness campaigns as essential strategies to enhance cybersecurity education and practices in these institutions.

Discussion of Findings

The role of cybersecurity awareness in safeguarding digital systems within Universities of Education is increasingly pivotal, particularly as these institutions expand their reliance on digital platforms for academic, administrative, and communication purposes. This study set out to examine the level of cybersecurity awareness among students and lecturers, identify key cybersecurity threats facing these institutions, and propose effective strategies for strengthening cybersecurity education. The findings revealed a moderate but uneven level of awareness across stakeholders. While academic and administrative staff demonstrated a relatively stronger grasp of cybersecurity principles such as password protection and phishing identification students showed weaker understanding of more advanced practices like two-factor authentication and institutional data protection protocols. This disparity reflects broader concerns in the literature that awareness is often stratified by role and access to training (Abdullahi et al., 2021; Aliyu et al., 2021), and highlights a crucial vulnerability: students, who are high-frequency users of institutional systems, may inadvertently become entry points for digital threats if not adequately trained.

The second objective exposed critical cybersecurity challenges facing Universities of Education. Respondents across all categories reported exposure to threats such as phishing scams, malware infections, identity theft, and the spread of misinformation through social engineering attacks. These findings echo previous studies (Aliyu et al., 2021; Vincent, 2024) that have warned of educational institutions being increasingly targeted due to insufficient IT security governance and a lack of regular user training. Administrative staff were most likely to identify these risks, possibly due to their direct engagement with institutional data systems, while students remained less able to recognize or respond to such threats. This underlines the need for a comprehensive, institution-wide security culture that does not isolate cybersecurity responsibilities to technical units alone but integrates it into the daily digital habits of all stakeholders.

To address these challenges, the study's third objective focused on strategies to enhance cybersecurity education and best practices. There was strong consensus across respondents in favor of mandatory cybersecurity training, curriculum integration, policy enforcement, and

periodic awareness campaigns. These strategies are consistent with global recommendations advocating for proactive, rather than reactive, cybersecurity frameworks in educational institutions (Bozkus Kahyaoglu & Caliyurt, 2018; Garba & Othman, 2021). However, implementation must go beyond surface-level awareness campaigns to include sustained investments in infrastructure, policy development, and capacity building. Without these enabling conditions, even well-designed strategies risk becoming performative rather than transformative. In sum, cybersecurity awareness plays a vital role not only in preventing breaches but also in cultivating a digitally responsible academic environment. Universities of Education must therefore prioritize structured, inclusive, and strategic cybersecurity education to safeguard their systems and ensure institutional resilience in an increasingly digital world.

Conclusion

This study has critically examined the role of cybersecurity awareness in safeguarding digital systems within Universities of Education. The findings underscore a moderate level of cybersecurity awareness among staff and a relatively lower awareness among students, particularly regarding advanced protective practices. The institutions face recurring cybersecurity threats—ranging from phishing and malware to misinformation and identity theft—which, if unaddressed, may compromise the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of educational data. Encouragingly, there is wide support among stakeholders for the implementation of structured strategies to promote cybersecurity education and best practices. These include the introduction of mandatory training, inclusion of cybersecurity in the curriculum, and the development of robust institutional policies. Ultimately, building a cybersecurity-conscious academic community requires a holistic, sustained, and inclusive approach that integrates awareness into the fabric of educational operations. The safeguarding of digital systems is no longer optional—it is a strategic imperative for institutional resilience in the digital age

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance digital safety and institutional preparedness:

1. Universities of Education should implement mandatory cybersecurity training programs tailored to the specific digital responsibilities and system access levels of students and staff to address the observed gaps in awareness and best practices.
2. The government should allocate dedicated funding to enhance ICT infrastructure in Universities of Education, including secure servers, reliable internet, and cybersecurity tools, to mitigate prevalent threats such as phishing, malware, and identity theft identified in the study.
3. A national cybersecurity policy framework specifically designed for tertiary institutions should be developed and enforced to ensure standardized practices in digital safety, data protection, and institutional compliance across all Universities of Education.
4. Cybersecurity awareness campaigns and digital literacy initiatives should be systematically incorporated into the academic calendar through consistent use of seminars, posters, and digital platforms to promote a culture of cybersecurity among students and staff.
5. Government agencies such as TETFund should provide continuous professional development opportunities and certification programs in cybersecurity and digital literacy to build the technical capacity of educators, administrators, and ICT personnel in Universities of Education

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